

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ADAPTIVE SCALING STRATEGIES: METHODS AND APPROACHES OF STARTUPS FOR ENTERING INTERNATIONAL MARKETS

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Abstract

This article explores approaches to analyzing adaptive scaling strategies employed by startups to enter international markets. Both traditional methods, such as franchising and licensing, and modern approaches, including the implementation of digital technologies and crowdsourcing solutions, are analyzed. It emphasizes that flexibility and consideration of local characteristics, such as cultural and legal differences, are essential conditions for successful market entry. The role of strategic planning, financial tools, and partnerships in strengthening startups' positions on the global stage is examined. The study is based on a comparative analysis of practical cases and highlights opportunities for innovative development and long-term business sustainability.

Keywords: scaling, startups, international markets, adaptive strategies, digital technologies, cultural adaptation, globalization.

Introduction

Scaling a business and entering international markets are critical stages in the development of startups in the era of globalization. Competition in local markets, increasing demand for innovation, and the rapid pace of technological advancement drive young companies to seek new growth opportunities beyond national borders. However, this process is accompanied by numerous challenges, including cultural differences, economic instability, and difficulties in adapting to new regulatory requirements. These challenges necessitate a well-thought-out approach based on adaptive strategies that provide flexibility and resilience in the face of diverse external factors.

The purpose of this study is to explore the methods and approaches used by startups to scale and successfully enter international markets. The research examines both traditional and innovative strategies that ensure competitiveness in a global context.

The relevance of this work is determined by the growing importance of internationalization in modern economic conditions and the need to develop universal and adaptive strategies for startups aiming to strengthen their positions in the global market. The methods employed in this study include a comparative analysis of internationalization strategies, a review of current literature on startup globalization, and an examination of empirical data and successful company cases.

Main part. Defining scaling in the business context

A startup is understood as a young, newly established company that develops innovative products, services, or business models, often leveraging modern technologies [1]. The primary goal of a startup is to quickly capture a market niche, scale its operations, and achieve sustainable profitability. According to the Startup Ranking, the largest number of startups in 2024 is registered in the U.S. (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Number of startups in different countries [2]

Scalability is one of the main elements of sustainable company growth. These metric approaches efficient systems and processes that will enable startups to

grow exponentially with as little additional cost as possible. Scaling involves optimizing internal operations,

implementing technologies, and leveraging network effects to capture a larger market share.

Scaling and expansion are commonly misused terms that need to be differentiated. Expansion is when the business expands physically by adding new branches, hiring personnel, or building up production capacity. This often corresponds to a massive increase in operation costs. In contrast, scaling emphasizes the creation of reproducible business models that enable growth with minimal expenses. For instance, startups utilizing digital platforms can serve an increasing num-

ber of clients without a substantial rise in staffing or infrastructure needs, which differentiates their approach from traditional expansion methods.

Classical methods for scaling startups to international markets

Startups employing classical methods can not only effectively expand their geographic reach but also access new markets with minimal time and resource expenditures. However, their success largely depends on careful planning, consideration of cultural and economic characteristics of target regions, and the willingness to adapt the product or service to local requirements (table 1).

Table 1.

Advantages and disadvantages of classical scaling method [3]

Method	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
Franchising	Granting rights to use the brand and business model for a fixed fee or royalties.	Rapid expansion with minimal costs. Use of resources and knowledge of local partners.	Loss of control over service quality. Dependence on franchisee performance.
Licensing	Transferring rights to use technologies, patents, or intellectual property.	Quick access to the market. No need to create infrastructure.	Risk of licensing violations. Limited profits from license fees.
Partnerships	Establishing strategic alliances with local companies.	Rapid market penetration. Shared use of resources and knowledge.	Potential conflicts of interest. Difficulty in managing partnership relationships.
Direct Investments	Creating branches or subsidiaries in new markets.	Full control over the business. Possibility of implementing long-term strategies.	High initial costs. Risk of economic instability in the target region.
Outsourcing	Engaging local companies to perform specific functions or tasks.	Reduced operational costs. Use of expertise from local performers.	Limited control over processes. Risks associated with compliance with quality standards.

Classical scaling methods for startups have proven their effectiveness in practice and remain relevant tools for entering international markets. Franchising and licensing provide possibilities of fast and relatively cheap access to new regions. Partnerships and direct investments give deeper market involvement and long-term potential. However, each method has its limitations, ranging from careful market condition, cultural specificities, to financial risk analyses. Their choice depends on the strategic goal of the startup, its resource base, and readiness to adapt to challenges of the global market. Put together, these approaches form a basis for successful business internationalization and strengthen its position in the global economy.

Innovative approaches to business scaling

Modern startups actively employ innovative approaches to scale their businesses, aiming to enhance efficiency and achieve rapid entry into new markets. One of the most in-demand methods is the implementation of digital technologies, which significantly simplify the process of adapting products or services to meet the needs of various regions [4]. Tools such as big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and cloud technologies help startups make more accurate decisions, minimize operational costs, and optimize resource management.

One of the successful applications of innovative use is associated with the development of digital platforms aimed at automating core business processes.

These allow optimizing customer interactions, personalizing offerings according to customers' needs, and integrating numerous sales channels. AI-driven software allows companies to analyze consumer behavioral patterns, predict demand, and enhance the quality of service delivered. These solutions also provide a chance for businesses to adapt their products to cultural peculiarities of target markets, making them more attractive to users.

Another critical area is the use of crowdsourcing and crowdfunding models. These approaches enable startups to attract funding, resources, or knowledge from a broad audience, reducing dependence on traditional investment sources. Crowdsourcing, for instance, provides an opportunity to create more relevant products by receiving direct feedback from target audiences. This is especially important when entering international markets, where needs and preferences can vary significantly.

Supply chain automation and logistics management technologies also play a vital role in innovative scaling. Software solutions such as blockchain ensure operational transparency, improve risk management, and foster trust among market participants. This is particularly relevant for international operations, where transparency and reliability are critical factors.

Startups employing innovative approaches prioritize flexibility and adaptability in their strategies. This enables them to respond more quickly to changes in the market environment and manage external challenges

more effectively [5]. However, implementing innovations requires substantial investments and skilled management to avoid risks associated with their complexity and technical execution. As a result, the use of innovative approaches gives startups a significant competitive advantage, making them more resilient in the face of global competition.

Adaptive tools for entering international markets

To successfully enter international markets, startups must use adaptive tools that help address differences in economic, cultural, and legal conditions. These approaches are based on the need to consider the specifics of the target market and flexibly adjust business strategies (table 2).

Table 2.

Examples of adaptive tools [6, 7]

Tool	Description	Example of application
Cultural adaptation	Accounting for the language, mentality, and preferences of consumers.	Localization of application interfaces, use of traditional symbols in advertising, adaptation of packaging.
Culturally-oriented marketing	Development of marketing campaigns based on local traditions and customs.	In Kazakhstan, emphasis on traditions and national values; in the U.S., focus on innovation and high technology.
Regulatory adaptation	Compliance with local legal norms, tax legislation, and quality standards.	Certification of products according to local standards and adapting to regional legal requirements.
Logistics and supply chain management	Adaptation of logistical processes to the region's infrastructure.	Selection of local suppliers, use of hybrid logistics schemes in regions with limited transport accessibility.
Financial strategy	Assessment of financial risks and resource allocation for market entry.	Attracting venture capital funds, hedging financial risks, and managing resource investments for sustainable expansion.
Investment in local projects	Support for local initiatives to build trust within the community.	Financing educational programs or launching charitable initiatives in the target region.

The use of adaptive tools is a necessary condition for the successful internationalization of startups. Cultural adaptation ensures effective interaction with local consumers, which is especially important in countries with pronounced cultural differences. Regulatory adaptation helps minimize legal risks and optimize operational processes [8]. A financial strategy enables the company to maintain stability, attract resources, and manage risks associated with entering new markets. The effectiveness of such tools depends on thorough preparation, a deep understanding of target regions, and strategic planning. A comprehensive approach to adaptation allows businesses not only to enter international markets but also to establish a strong foothold, creating long-term competitiveness.

Examples of successful scaling by various companies

American startups demonstrate high efficiency in scaling their businesses to international markets. One notable example is the startup **Deel**, which provides a platform for managing international teams and payroll. Thanks to its flexibility and compliance with local regulations, the company has attracted over 35,000 clients, enabling it to expand its presence to more than 150 markets.

Another example is **Miro**, an American startup offering a cloud-based platform for visual collaboration. Initially created as a tool for team project work and brainstorming in remote environments, Miro has significantly expanded its functionality and customer base since 2020. By 2024, Miro serves over 80 million users worldwide across 200,000 organizations, including Nike, IKEA, Deloitte, WPP, and Cisco. This makes it one of the most successful startups in its niche.

Kazakhstani startups also showcase successful examples of scaling. One of the leaders is **Kaspi.kz**, which began its operations as a financial organization. With the advancement of technology, the company developed a mobile application that provided customers with convenient access to financial services. In 2020, Kaspi.kz went public on the London Stock Exchange. This strengthened its reputation and allowed it to attract international investors. Today, the company holds leading positions not only in Kazakhstan but also in the markets of Central Asia.

Another example is **Chocofamily**. Initially, the startup offered a group-buying service but later transformed into an ecosystem of online services. It now includes food delivery, flight booking, and medical services. The startup caught the attention of international funds and used their investments to enter new markets in Central Asia. This enabled the company to build a scalable business model and lay the foundation for further growth.

Companies from the United States and Kazakhstan demonstrate different approaches to scaling, reflecting the unique characteristics of their markets and economic realities. American companies focus on innovation, flexibility, and technological leadership. They actively adapt their platforms to the cultural and economic conditions of target markets, emphasizing localization of services and ensuring compliance with legal norms. Additionally, significant attention is given to attracting major venture capital investments, enabling aggressive expansion.

Kazakhstani companies focus on building long-term strategies, integrating local solutions, and developing sustainable business models. Particular emphasis

is placed on using digital technologies to enhance service accessibility and expand their customer base. Kazakhstani companies often start by dominating their national market before transitioning to scaling in neighboring countries. This approach is driven by the need to account for the economic, infrastructural, and cultural characteristics of the region.

Conclusion

Adaptive scaling strategies employed by startups to enter international markets emphasize the importance of flexibility, innovation, and consideration of local characteristics in target regions. Successful scaling requires a combination of traditional methods, such as franchising and licensing, with modern approaches, including the use of digital technologies and crowdsourcing. Examples of successful startups demonstrate that implementing cultural adaptation, complying with local regulations, and strategic planning are critically important elements for establishing a strong position in the global market. However, achieving sustainable growth necessitates investments in technology, risk management, and the development of partnerships, ensuring long-term competitiveness and resilience in a global competitive environment.

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